

Mixed ligand (acetylacetonato)(chlorophenoxy)zirconium(IV) complexes and their reactivity

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Zr^{IV} complexes of composition ZrCl_{2-n}(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II})_n where *n* = 1, 2, acac = -C₅H₇O₂ (acetylacetonate anion), OAr^I = OC₆H₄-Cl-*o* and OAr^{II} = OC₆H₄-Cl-*p* have been prepared and characterized by elemental analyses, molecular weight, molar conductance, IR and ¹H NMR data. The donor complexes, ZrCl(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II}) react with Lewis acids (FeCl₃ and PCl₅) in nitrobenzene at 25 ± 1°C to produce [Zr(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II})]⁺[FeCl₄]⁻ and [Zr(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II})]⁺[PCl₆]⁻.

Zirconium(IV) phenoxides¹⁻³ have drawn comparatively far less attention in comparison to its alkoxide complexes, possibly due to tedious procedures required for the preparation of the former. The present paper describes the synthesis and characterization of some new zirconium(IV) aryloxides by reacting dichlorobis(acetylacetonate)zirconium(IV) and *o*- and *p*-chlorophenols using diethylamine as HCl acceptor and study of their reactions with Lewis acids FeCl₃ and PCl₅ in nitrobenzene.

Results and discussion

The addition of a mixture of substituted chlorophenol and diethylamine to the solution of dichloro bis(acetylacetonate)zirconium(IV) in dry benzene in predetermined molar ratios at room temperature affords the convenient formation of complexes in good yields as :

(where *n* = 1 or 2)

The stoichiometric formulations are in conformity with elemental analyses (Table 1). The resulting complexes are light yellow to brown solids, soluble in CHCl₃, CCl₄ and some other common organic solvents. The low molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions of the complexes in nitrobenzene at 25 ± 1°C suggest their non-electrolytic nature. The molecular weight determinations (Rast's-Camphor method) indicate them to be monomers.

IR spectra : In the IR spectra of the complexes, there is a complete absence of bands in the 3480–3390 cm⁻¹ region

due to the hydrogen bonded phenolic (-OH) group of the free phenols⁴ suggesting thereby their deprotonation to form Et₂NH.HCl during the course of reaction (1). The bands at 1620, 1520, 1480 and 1422 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν(C=C) of the phenolic ring shifts slightly towards higher regions. The most important and strong band present at 1250 cm⁻¹ in chlorophenols assigned to ν(C-O) mode is significantly lowered (60–80 cm⁻¹), suggesting a considerable contribution from a structure of type M-O-C, wherein drainage of electron density from the ring to the metal through C-O bond occurs. Sharp bands around 1358 and 1338 cm⁻¹ due to ν(ring) + δ(OH) of the parent ligands are missing in all these compounds. Appearance of entirely new bands in the region 590–578 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν(Zr-O) modes⁵. The bands around 360–340 cm⁻¹ of complexes ZrCl(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II}), may be assigned to ν(Zr-Cl) modes.

¹H NMR spectra : The complete absence of resonances around δ 4.78 ppm due to phenolic proton in ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes ZrCl(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II}) and Zr(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II})₂, supports the formation of complexes through deprotonation of phenolic OH group, inline with IR spectral observations. The appearance of signals due to aromatic ring protons as a multiplet in δ 6.9–7.3 ppm range, which are slightly downfield compared to those in pure *o*- and *p*-chlorophenols in δ 6.67–7.10 ppm range, may be the result of coordination of phenolic oxygen to zirconium⁶. The signals at δ 2.05 and 5.5 ppm observed in ZrCl₂(acac)₂ due to methyl protons and ethylenic proton of the acetylacetonate group remain almost unaltered in the complexes⁷. The integration of signals due to acetylacetonate and aryloxide ligands agrees well with the proposed stoichiometry of the

Table 1. Analytical data of the complexes

Compd.*	Colour	Elemental analysis (%) :		Molar conductance in PhNO ₂ (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Molecular weight Found (Reqd.)
		Found (Reqd.)			
		Zr	Cl		
ZrCl ₂ (acac) ₂	Dirty white	25.54 (25.31)	19.64 (19.71)	0.9	360 (360.2)
ZrCl(acac) ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>o</i>)	Yellow	20.56 (20.16)	22.34 (21.88)	1.5	430 (452.2)
ZrCl(acac) ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>)	Brown	20.21 (20.16)	21.52 (21.88)	0.6	433 (452.2)
Zr(acac) ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>o</i>) ₂	Yellow	16.90 (16.75)	27.20 (27.24)	1.8	515 (544.2)
Zr(acac) ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>) ₂	Brown	16.80 (16.75)	23.10 (23.15)	1.4	530 (544.2)
Zr(acac) ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>o</i>).FeCl ₄	Reddish brown	14.79 (14.84)	23.07 (23.10)	23.51	595 (614.54)
Zr(acac) ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>).FeCl ₄	Reddish brown	14.81 (14.84)	23.09 (23.10)	16.10	605 (614.54)
Zr(acac) ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>o</i>).PCl ₆	Pale yellow	13.78 (13.80)	32.21 (32.23)	26.33	645 (660.67)
Zr(acac) ₂ (OC ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>).PCl ₆	Pale yellow	13.79 (13.80)	32.22 (32.23)	19.29	655 (660.67)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analyses.

complexes, thus confirming their formation according to (1).

Reaction of ZrCl(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II}) with FeCl₃ and PCl₅ : 10⁻³ M solutions of these complexes [ZrCl(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II})] in nitrobenzene show very low conductivities but the addition of 10⁻³ M solutions of FeCl₃ and PCl₅ in the same solvent results in an increase in the conductivity of the solution. Conductance composition curves reveal discontinuities at 1 : 1 molar ratio, which are indicative of the formation of 1 : 1 compounds. In the light of the above observations, the reactions of [ZrCl(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II})] with FeCl₃ and PCl₅ in 1 : 1 molar ratio in CCl₄ + MeOH mixture solution were undertaken. The elemental analyses (Table 1) of the isolated compounds correspond to the [ZrCl(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II}).FeCl₃] and [ZrCl(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II}).PCl₅] respectively and molar conductivities of their millimolar solutions in nitrobenzene agree reasonably well for 1 : 1 electrolytes⁸ i.e. [Zr(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II})]⁺ [FeCl₄]⁻ and [Zr(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II})]⁺ [PCl₆]⁻ respectively.

Appearance of new and sharp bands at 358 and 385 cm⁻¹ of these 1 : 1 compounds can be ascribed to the respective PCl₆⁻ and FeCl₄⁻ anions respectively⁹. The absence of an absorption band due to ν_{Zr-Cl} mode further supports their formation.

Experimental

Zirconium tetrachloride was purified by sublimation. *o*-

Chlorophenol, acetylacetone and diethylamine were distilled before use. Solvents and other chemicals were dried before use. Dichlorobis(acetylacetonate)zirconium(IV) was prepared by the published procedure¹⁰. The infrared spectra (KBr pellets) were recorded on (4000–200 cm⁻¹) a Beckmann IR 4250 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on Joel JNM PMX 60 SI spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Conductance measurements in nitrobenzene were carried out at 25 ± 1°C using digital conductivity bridge NDC-732. Molecular weights were determined by Rast's-Camphor method. Zirconium was estimated gravimetrically as ZrO₂ and chlorine by Volhard's method.

Preparation of bis(acetylacetonate)zirconium(IV) phenoxides ZrCl_{2-n}(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II})_n (where n = 1 or 2) : In a typical reaction, to a solution of dichloro bis(acetylacetonate)zirconium(IV) (1.5 g, 0.004 mol) in dry benzene, two equivalents of chlorophenol (1.06 g, 0.008 mol) in the same solvent were added using diethylamine as HCl acceptor. The reaction mixture was initially stirred followed by heating under reflux for 3–4 h to ensure the completion of reaction. The Et₂NH.HCl formed was then removed by filtration. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness under vacuum. The solid so obtained was dried under vacuum and was recrystallised from CCl₄. Yield of Zr(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II})₂ was 80%. A similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of ZrCl(acac)₂(OAr^{I,II}).

Reaction of $ZrCl(acac)_2(OAr^{I,II})$ with $FeCl_3$ and PCl_5 :

The complexes of composition $ZrCl(acac)_2(OAr^{I,II})_2.FeCl_3$ were synthesized by reacting $ZrCl(acac)_2(OAr^{I,II})$ with $FeCl_3$ in 1 : 1 molar ratio using $CCl_4 + MeOH$ as solvent under stirring followed by refluxing. From the solution, complexes were extracted with the addition of petroleum ether and dried under vacuum. Complexes of composition $ZrCl(acac)_2(OAr^{I,II}).PCl_5$ were prepared by similar methodology.

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